

CONTEXTUAL FEATURES OF MODALITY IN WRITTEN DISCOURSE

Ahadova Hulkaroy Zarifxon qizi

EFL teacher, UzSWLU

Abstract: In our developed world, it is becoming significant to investigate different features of language aspects and analyzing its representation in written discourse. The current thesis statement delves into contextual features of modality in written discourse. The general notion about modality and its usage is being overviewed through textual contexts.

Key words: Modality, discourse, context, features, textual.

The category which conveys necessity and possibility of happening events are considered as modality in linguistics. In the place of possibilities, the modalized sentence places the underlying or antecedent concept (the word antecedent was introduced by medieval logicians). Ann should be at home claims that Ann is most likely at home. As long as the statement represents that it is possible that Ann is at home. The temporal analogue of modality should be called "temporality", although the main verbal manifestations of temporality, time and aspect are more often used. Modality and temporality are at the heart of the "displacement" trait (one of Charles F. Hockett's aspects of human language design), that permits natural language to discuss current situations.

Modality at the level of a sentence-statement has been sufficiently studied and is usually defined as a category expressing the attitude of the speaker to the content of the statement (subjective modality) and the relation of the latter to reality (objective modality). In the first case, modality is created by specific modal words, particles, interjections (fortunately, unfortunately, alas, etc.); in the second case, modality is created primarily by the mood forms of verbs and words expressing the meaning of statements, possibilities, wishes, orders, etc.

Objective modality, in fact, reflects how the speaker (author) qualifies reality - as real or unreal, possible, desirable, etc. Thus, modality is realized at the lexical, grammatical and intonational level.

However, the category of modality can be taken out of the sentence-statement - into the text and speech situation (V.Vinogradov, 1971). Then the pragmatics of this category expands significantly and the act of communication itself comes to the fore, i.e. relationship between author and reader.

To understand the image of the author, it is necessary to clarify some specifics of this object. And it, in particular, is directly related to the disclosure of the essence of the concept of accuracy. Accuracy is a necessary condition for scientific definitions and explanations. However, the accuracy itself is different in different sciences. Thus, accuracy in literary criticism must be understood in a special way; We are interested in literary criticism insofar as the concept of the image of the author arose in the depths of philology, already in literary criticism. And initially it was applied only in relation to fiction (academician V.V. Vinogradov). Here the requirement of accuracy is not absolute; in any case, it raises the question of the degree of accuracy allowed.

The fact is that the concept of the image of the author, being inaccurate from the point of view of the exact sciences, turns out to be quite accurate for literary criticism, if we accept the idea of a special nature of accuracy in artistic creativity. The image of the author, of course, is created in a literary work by speech means, since without a verbal form there is no work itself, but this image is created by the reader. It is in the field of perception, perception, of course, given by the author, and not always given by the will of the author himself. Precisely because the image of the author is more related to the sphere of perception, rather than material expression, difficulties arise in the exact definition of this concept. Although, of course, the image of the author is created on the basis of the structure of the text. By the way, after all, there are many such concepts, difficult to grasp and define, although undoubtedly existing, in science, take, for example, the same subtext.

The perception of the author's personality through the forms of its embodiment in the text is a two-way process. It focuses on the relationship between author and reader. The modality of the text is the expression in the text of the author's attitude to what is being reported, his concept, point of view, position, his value orientations, formulated for the sake of communicating to their reader.

This author's assessment of what is depicted is always associated with the search for adequate ways of expression. The ways of expressing this attitude and evaluation can be different, selective for each author and type of text, they are motivated and purposeful.

Above the choice of these methods, there is always, therefore, some kind of non-speech task, the implementation of which creates its own modality of the text. General modality as an expression of the author's attitude to what is being reported makes one perceive the text not as the sum of individual units, but as a whole work. Such perception is based not on the consideration of the qualities of individual speech units, but on the establishment of their functions as part of the whole.

It can be concluded that there is a real speech producer in any work, of any type and genre of literature. This authorship is embodied in different forms of the subject of the narrative: the impersonal form prevails in official and business works, although here, too, genre specificity shakes the general impersonality (autobiography, statement, complaint, etc.).

References:

1. Biber, Douglas, Stig Johansson, Geoffrey Leech, Susan Conrad, & Edward Finnegan. 1999. Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English.
2. David Lewis. 1979. “A Problem about Permission”. In Essays in Honour of Jaako Hintikka: On the Occasion of His Fiftieth Birthday on January 12, 1979
3. Hacquard, V. & Wellwood, A. (2012). Embedding epistemic modals in English: A corpus-based study. *Semantics and Pragmatics*. Vol. 5(4), 1-29.
4. John MacFarlane. 2003. “Epistemic Modalities and Relative Truth”.
5. Paul Teller. 1972. “Epistemic Possibility”. *Philosophia*, 2: 302–320.